

EFFECT OF IRON-DEPOSITED REDUCED GRAPHENE OXIDES ON THE NEAR-FIELD ELECTROMAGNETIC ABSORBING PROPERTY OF COMPOSITE FILMS

J. W. Yi^{1,2*}, S. B. Lee², B. M. Jung², H. S. Choe², S. K. Lee², K. H. Kim³, O. O. Park¹

¹ Department of Chemical & Biomolecular Engineering, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology, Daejeon, Korea

² Composites Research Center, Korea Institute of Materials Science, Changwon, Korea

³ Department of Physics, Yeungnam University, Gyeongsan, Korea

* Corresponding author (yjw0628@kims.re.kr)

Keywords: *Composites, Electromagnetic, Absorption, Graphene, Iron*

1 Introduction

Recently, since the use of electronic devices rapidly increases, GHz electromagnetic (EM) waves are increasingly applied in various applications due to the saturation at lower frequency bands. At the same time, these electronic devices are getting smaller and thinner. In these applications, recent issues of the high-frequency electromagnetic waves are electromagnetic interference (EMI), noise generation and reduction of harmful waves to human body. In particular, it has been well-known that these waves do damage to the human body and electronic devices resulting in malfunctions.

With these increased usages of electronic devices, much attention has been paid to avoiding EMI between the electrical component and signal source. In near-field ($kr \ll 1$), where k is wavenumber and r is the distance from an EM wave source to detectors, it is very essential that signal integrity should be maintained and concurrently noise should be reduced [1]. To suppress only the EM noise and signal interference, loss generation by magnetic resonance has been utilized. The EM noise suppression can be performed more effectively by the absorption mechanism using the magnetic loss than by simple shielding.

Composite magnetic films have been applied as an EM wave absorber in near-field application. These films for EMI shielding or noise suppressing usually comprise semi-hard magnetic powder of a magnetic metal alloy having a high coercive force and an organic reagent or polymeric material for binding

the magnetic powder [2]. However, since these particles such as Fe-Si-Al flakes are very heavy, it is difficult to fabricate lightweight EM absorbers.

Several studies have been performed on the fabrication of lightweight magnetic metal particles. Kim [3] proposed hollow ceramic microspheres plated with a Co-Fe thin layer. An average diameter of the microspheres was about $70\mu\text{m}$ and the thickness of metal layer was approximately $2\mu\text{m}$. Wei [4] prepared hollow glass spheres coated with Fe_3O_4 films by a ferrite plating method. Jiang [5] prepared Ni/polymer spheres using polystyrene particles as templates by an ultrasonic electroless plating method and a subsequent heat treatment. The hollow metal fibers were also fabricated by employing an electrospinning [6], impregnation/thermal treatment [7], and electroless plating method [8, 9].

In our previous work, we have proposed a hollow magnetic fiber as lightweight magnetic filler for EM wave absorbers [10]. However, this filler also has some limitations, for instance, difficulty in increasing the concentration in the polymer matrix due to the low processability resulting in an insufficient EM absorbance.

In order to overcome such limitations, Fe-deposited reduced graphene oxide (rGO) as auxiliary magnetic filler. It is also expected that the filler can give a clue to fabricate lightweight EM absorbers. In addition, the filler orients at in-plane direction inside the composite film due to the 2D structure originating from the rGO. This orientation can

enhance the absorbing property of the composite films compared to the films with randomly-distributed Fe particles. In this work, we will investigate the effect of Fe-deposited rGO or the hybrid filler system with conventional magnetic particles on the near-field EM absorbing performance.

2 Experimentals

2.1 Fabrication of Fe-deposited rGO

Graphene oxide (GO) was prepared by modified Hummers method. 100mg of GO was added to the 100ml of deionized (DI) water and treated by a sonication. 54 mg of FeSO_4 was dissolved in 50ml of DI water and this solution was poured to the aqueous GO solution and stirred for 12 hours at room temperature. Next, NaBH_4 was added to the mixture to reduce the Fe ion and GO. After the reduction, the solution was filtered and washed with an excess amount of water. The remnant was dried at a vacuum oven. The samples were thermally treated under the condition of 500°C and Argon atmosphere for 2 hours.

2.2 Composite films with Fe-deposited rGO

A hollow magnetic fiber consisting of an inner layer of nickel (Ni) and outer layer of iron-cobalt (Fe-Co, atomic ratio 5:5) was used as primary magnetic filler [10]. For a comparison, Fe nanoparticles were fabricated by the same method as Fe-deposited rGO. Hybrid composite films including Fe-deposited rGO and the hollow magnetic fibers were fabricated by a doctor blade with different thicknesses. Firstly, the mixtures of a binder resin, hollow magnetic fiber and Fe-deposited rGO were processed by a three-roll-milling for better dispersion followed by being cast on the easy-off substrate film. Filler concentrations of the hybrid composite films were listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Compositions of the hybrid composites

Materials	1	2	3
Binder resin	50	48	48
Hollow magnetic fiber (HF)	50	50	50
Fe-deposited rGo (GO/Fe)	-	2	-
Fe particle (Fe)	-	-	2

2.3 Characterizations

FE-SEM/EDS were used for the observation of surface morphology and their element composition of Fe-deposited rGO. X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the filler were obtained to investigate phase composition and degree of phase change using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation with a voltage of 40 kV and a generator current of 40 mA (Rigaku, D/max 2200). The scanning rate and the interval were $5^\circ/\text{min}$ and 0.02° , respectively.

Saturation moment, remnant moment and coercive force of the filler were measured by a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM). In order to near-field EM power loss in the frequency range of $\sim 8\text{GHz}$ was evaluated by a micro strip line (MSL) [1]. Figure 1 shows the schematics of the measurement system.

Fig. 1. Schematics of the near-field EM wave absorbing device

3 Results and Discussion

In general, the synthetic route of graphene can be mainly categorized by two methods: dry and wet process. In case of the dry processes such as chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and epitaxial growth, some researchers have already reported that nearly 30-inch graphene films can be grown on the metallic substrates of Ni and copper (Cu) under a high temperature condition. However, these kinds of method are not cost-effective and the yield is low. Moreover, they are not suitable for mass production.

Since a wide range of potential applications including graphene has been considered, more

EFFECT OF IRON-DEPOSITED REDUCED GRAPHENE OXIDES ON THE NEAR-FIELD ELECTROMAGNETIC ABSORBING PROPERTY OF COMPOSITE FILMS

economical and more facile fabrication method for graphene is a solution-based method. The method is an attractive technique, in particular, for the production on a large scale. Typical solution-based method can provide a large amount of GO which is made from low-priced graphite particles by a chemical oxidation/exfoliation. GO can be changed into rGO by chemical or thermal treatments. In addition, GO retains several active functional groups (Epoxy, hydroxyl and carboxylic acid etc.) on which some particles can be deposited. It can be also dispersed homogeneously in the polymeric materials due to the functional groups.

Fig. 2 shows the surface SEM images of Fe-deposited rGO with different reducing reaction times. According to the results, the growth of Fe nanoparticles on the surface of rGO after adding the reducing agent was observed. It is probable that the growth on the surface is attributed to the electrostatic interaction between the positive charge of Fe ion and the negative charge of carboxylic acid of GO. The size of the Fe nanoparticles was approximately 15~60nm. It was seen that the nanoparticles were uniformly deposited on the basal plane of rGO. EDS analysis confirmed that the nanoparticles were Fe and Fe oxide.

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs and EDS of Fe-deposited rGO with different reducing reaction times: (a) 30 min, (b) 90 min, (c) 120 min and (d) EDS of (c).

The XRD patterns of Fe-deposited rGO before and after heat treatment are shown in Figure 3. The heat

treatment is capable of crystallizing the amorphous Fe portion as well as reducing the substrate GO. On the other hand, it can induce the oxidation of Fe. Diffraction peaks at 2 theta values of 30.0°, 35.4° and 62.5° of the sample (Figure 3(a)) correspond to the oxidized Fe reflection; Fe₂O₃ and Fe₃O₄. 2 theta values of 44.5° and 82.5° correspond to the Fe reflection. In figure 3(b), the peak intensities of the oxidized form were increased and all of the peaks were sharper. From the XRD analysis, it is expected that heat treatment increases the amount of the oxidized phases and also fortified their crystalline structures. The crystalline can improve the magnetic properties of the Fe-deposited rGO.

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of Fe-deposited rGO; (a) before heat treatment and (b) after heat treatment.

The saturated magnetic moments of the Fe-deposited rGO with 120 min reaction time and neat rGO were measured by a VSM. The paper samples of neat rGO and Fe-deposited rGO for VSM were prepared by a vacuum filtering method. Fig. 3 shows the profiles of the magnetic moment of the samples. Neat rGO had no magnetic property throughout the external

magnetic field as expected. In case of Fe-deposited rGO, the saturated magnetic moment was around 3 emu/g and the remnant coercive force from the hysteresis was very low. Because the Fe particles were deposited on the rGO, the slightly higher saturated magnetic moment than that of neat rGO was observed. However, since very small amount of nano size Fe particles on the rGO was sparsely deposited, the magnetic properties themselves were considered as negligible.

Fig. 4. Magnetic moments of rGO and Fe-deposited rGO

The thin film composite absorbers with different filler systems shown in Table 1 were fabricated to measure the near-field absorbing property. Figure 5 shows the images of fabricated composites cut in 50mm x 50mm. The thicknesses of all of the films were approximately 110µm.

Fig. 5. Picture of the fabricated composite absorbers

Fig. 6. Power losses of the film type composite absorbers by measured by MSL.

The near-field absorbing property of the composite films was evaluated by a power loss divided by input power from 500MHz to 6GHz. The power loss/input power was calculated by the equation shown below.

$$P_{loss}/P_{in}=1-([S_{21}]^2+[S_{11}]^2) \quad (1)$$

where S_{21} and S_{11} are scattering parameters of the reflection and transmission, respectively.

The results were shown in figure 6. MSL means the power loss without any absorber. The power loss of the reference absorber with only hollow magnetic fiber was measured at ~0.5 at 6GHz. This implies that 50% of the input power was absorbed by the film. As seen in the figure, the power loss of the hybrid filler (HF+Fe nanoparticles) was 0.53. This slightly increase indicated that the randomly distributed Fe nanoparticles in the polymer matrix have negligible effect on the improvement of the absorber with the hollow magnetic fibers. The film absorber with the hollow fiber and Fe-deposited rGO showed the highest power loss and the value (~0.8 at 6GHz) was dramatically increased. This result indicates that Fe-deposited rGO which were aligned on in-plane direction throughout the film can play a role in connecting the magnetic field originated from the signal among the hollow fibers. From the result, it is expected that Fe-deposited rGO is a good

secondary magnetic filler for improving the near-field composite absorber.

4 Conclusion

In order to increase the efficiency of near-field absorbers with only hollow magnetic fibers, it is expected that a continuous network inside the absorber is necessary. Fe nanoparticles deposited on the graphene oxide were newly fabricated to interconnect the hollow magnetic fibers in the matrix. According to the experimental results, it is probable that Fe-deposited rGO act as a subsidiary magnetic network resulting in high power loss.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by a grant from the basic research program of Korea Institute of Materials Science (KIMS) and GRL research program, Republic of Korea.

References

- [1] B. Nam, Y. H. Choa, S. T. Oh, S. K. Lee and K. H. Kim "Broadband RF Noise Suppression by Magnetic Nanowire-Filled Composite Films", *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, Vol. 45, pp 2777-2781, 2009.
- [2] H. Ono, S. Yoshida, S. Ando and Y. Shimada "Improvement of the electromagnetic-noise suppressing features for Fe-Si-Al composite sheets by dc magnetic field biasing", *Journal of Applied Physics*, Vol. 93, No.10, pp 6662- 6668, 2003.
- [3] S.S. Kim, S.T. Kim, J.M. Ahn, K.H. Kim "Magnetic and microwave absorbing properties of Co-Fe thin films plated on hollow ceramic microspheres of low density", *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, Vol. 271, pp 39-45, 2004.
- [4] J. Wei, J. Liu, S. Li "Electromagnetic and microwave absorption properties of Fe₃O₄ magnetic films plated on hollow glass spheres", *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, Vol. 312, pp 414-417, 2007.
- [5] J. Jiang, H. Lu, L. Zhang, N. Xu "Preparation of monodisperse Ni/PS spheres and hollow nickel spheres by ultrasonic electroless plating", *Surface and Coatings Technology*, Vol. 201, pp 7174-7179, 2007.
- [6] D. Li, Y. Xia "Direct Fabrication of Composite and Ceramic Hollow Nanofibers by Electrospinning", *ACS Nano Letters*, Vol. 4 (5), pp 933-938, 2004.
- [7] R. Yuan, X. Fu X, X. Wang, P. Liu, L. Wu, Y. Xu, X. Wang, Z. Wang "Template Synthesis of Hollow Metal Oxide Fibers with Hierarchical Architecture", *Chemistry of Materials*, Vol. 18 (19), pp 4700-4705, 2006.
- [8] H. Zhang, Y. Liu "Preparation and microwave properties of Ni hollow fiber by electroless plating-template method", *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, Vol. 458, pp 588-594, 2008.
- [9] H. Lu, J. Yao, L. Zhang, Y. Wang, J. Tian, N. Xu "Preparation of Ni/TiO₂ composite hollow fibers by electroless plating", *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, Vol. 466, pp 218-222, 2007.
- [10] J. W. Yi, S. B. Lee, J. B. Kim, S. K. Lee "Fabrication of ultrafine hollow Ni and Ni/Fe fibers and their dispersion characteristics in the epoxy matrix", *Surface and Coatings Technology*, Vol. 204, pp 1419-1425, 2010.